

Welcome to the DATAMITE Newsletter

Our motto: Unleashing the Monetisation Potential of Data.

Webinar series - Unlocking Data Value with DATAMITE!

We are launching a new series of webinars to showcase the work carried out at DATAMITE over the last years. The following webinars are already available:

Legal Frameworks for Data Ethical Compliance

The banner features a dark blue background with a pattern of white dots at the bottom. On the right, there is a circular graphic with a hand pointing at it, containing icons for scales of justice, a person, and a house. A red YouTube play button is overlaid on the text. The text on the left reads: 'UNLOCKING DATA VALUE WITH DATAMITE WEBINAR SERIES' and 'LEGAL FRAMEWORKS FOR DATA TRADING: ENSURING LEGAL AND ETHICAL COMPLIANCE'. On the right, it says '11 SEPTEMBER 2025 11:00 - 12:00 CET' and 'ONLINE'. At the bottom right, it lists 'LAW AND INTERNET FOUNDATION (LIF)' with a person icon.

On 18 September, Polina Petrova from [Law and Internet Foundation](#) and Margit Hofer from [Centre for Social Innovation \(ZSI\)](#) launched our new webinar series:

'Unlocking Data Value with DATAMITE'. They delivered a one-hour webinar exploring the legal frameworks for data trading. You can view the presentation [here](#).

Data Valuation: Maximizing Business Potential

On 2 October, Rob Schneider from [FIR an der RWTH Aachen](#), Margit Hofer from [Centre for Social Innovation \(ZSI\)](#) and Eduardo Vyhmeister from [University College Cork](#) delivered the second webinar in our 'Unlocking Data Value with DATAMITE' series, exploring data valuation. You can view the presentation [here](#).

Data Monetization: Organizational Maturity and Strategies for Implementation

UNLOCKING DATA VALUE WITH DATAMITE
WEBINAR SERIES

DATA MONETIZATION: ORGANIZATIONAL MATURITY AND STRA FOR IMPLEMENTA

1001 LAKES

09 OCTOBER 2025
11:00 - 12:00 CET

ONLINE

On 9 October, Udo Bub from [1001 Lakes](#), delivered the third webinar in our 'Unlocking Data Value with DATAMITE' series, exploring data monetisation. You can view the presentation [here](#).

Consultation European Commission for the Forthcoming Data Union Strategy

VIEWS OF THE DATAMITE CONSORTIUM

Consultation European Commission for the Forthcoming Data Union Strategy: Views of the DATAMITE Consortium

In line with its policy of contributing to open science and having a real impact on European data policies, **DATAMITE is making its views on the European**

Commission's consultation for the forthcoming Data Union Strategy available to everyone.

Law and Internet Foundation, a DATAMITE partner, has written a policy brief in which DATAMITE aims to contribute to and enhance the forthcoming New European Strategy for Data.

[Discover more](#)

EVENTS

The poster features a dark blue background with orange and white text. At the top right, a yellow ribbon says 'Save the date!'. The main text reads 'Open Source Community Day', 'Date: 23 - 24 September', and 'Location: Madrid, Spain'. It also mentions 'Co-located with AIOTI Days 2025'. At the bottom, logos for 'ECLIPSE FOUNDATION' and 'CEI-Sphere part of EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu' are displayed.

The Open Source Community Day 2025

The **Open Source Community Day**, organised by the **Eclipse Foundation** in collaboration with **EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu** took place in Madrid on 23 and 24 September. As part of the event's dissemination and collaboration activities, a community session was hosted where participants could present their ongoing research, open-source initiatives and project outcomes. **DATAMITE was one of the projects presented** by the Eclipse Foundation, as they are part of our consortium.

[Discover more](#)

DATAMITE at the APMS Conference

The **APMS Conference** took place in Kamakura, Japan, from 31 August to 4 September. The conference featured original, high-impact academic contributions as part of its programme, with a paper on **DATAMITE** being one of the selected works. Martin Loers, from DATAMITE's partner **FIR an der RWTH Aachen**, presented the paper "Supporting Strategic Decision Making for Data Monetization in the Era of Digital Transformation".

[Discover more](#)

DATAMITE at the AI Connected Business World 2025

DATAMITE at the AI Connected Business World

2025

The **15th AI Connected Business World** took place on 24 June in Athens, Greece. The aim of the conference was to bring together key figures in innovation, including representatives from local government, businesses, research institutions and start-ups. Among them was **DATAMITE partner OTE Group of Companies** (OTE), who attended the event and presented the project at their stand. They promoted DATAMITE at the booth using an **informative roll-up banner and a virtual assistant** to engage with visitors and talk to them about the project.

[Discover more](#)

International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI) 2025

The 2025 International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (**AIAI**) was held from 26 – 29 June in a Hybrid format, in Limassol, Cyprus, and online. AIAI is a renowned international conference that brings together scientists and researchers each year to exchange the latest and most cutting-edge advances in the field. Its programme includes workshops that provide an ideal setting for the presentation of leading-edge conference papers.

For the second consecutive year, **DATAMITE** was well represented at the conference by its partner, OTE.

[Discover more](#)

DELIVERABLES

Between late June and late September, the DATAMITE consortium submitted several deliverables to the European Commission. All public deliverables are based on key principles that ensure transparency, reproducibility, and broad public awareness throughout the research process. These new public deliverables are now available for anyone to read.

- **Deliverable 1.4 - Requirements and Architecture:**
 - This document provides an update on the technical and functional analysis of the components' requirements and the DATAMITE framework's architecture. A requirements analysis is carried out, and a detailed view of the architecture is presented following the C4 approach. Read the deliverable [here](#).
- **D2.4 - Data Sharing and Sovereignty Mechanisms:**
 - This document outlines the status of the data sharing and sovereignty mechanisms. It provides a detailed explanation of the design overview, the applied technologies, the current implementation status, the next steps, and any encountered issues and obstacles for the components related to Work Package: Data Sharing Mechanisms and Data. Finally, it discusses the established communication channels. Read the deliverable [here](#).
- **D2.5 - Data Sharing and Sovereignty Mechanisms (Final Development Status):**
 - This deliverable outlines the final development status of the data sharing and data sovereignty mechanisms. It includes references to the repository, open API specifications, online documentation, and other resources for each component related to Work Package: Data Sharing Mechanisms and Data Sovereignty. Read the deliverable [here](#).
- **D3.3 - Design and Implementation of the Data Governance, Quality, and Security Modules:**
 - This document describes the components related to Work Package: Data Governance, Quality, Security and Support Modules, providing

information about their design overview and, regarding their implementation, previous and final status. Read the deliverable [here](#).

- **D3.5 - Data Governance Quality and Security Modules:**

- This deliverable outlines the current development status of the Data Governance, Quality and Security Modules. It includes references to the repository, open API specifications, online documentation, and other resources for each component related to Work Package: Data Governance, Quality, Security and Support Modules. Read the deliverable [here](#).

- **Deliverable 4.2 - Basic Dataset Computation Approach and Structured KPI Catalogue for the Valuation of Datasets:**

- This deliverable presents a structured framework for objectively valuing datasets, combining theoretical foundations and practical tools. Beginning with a systematic literature review across leading academic databases, it identifies and categorises over 100 data valuation metrics and key performance indicators (KPIs) into a coherent taxonomy aligned with the four perspectives of the Balanced Scorecard. The taxonomy clusters metrics under Data Valuation Techniques, Data Monetisation, Data Quality & Governance, Operational Efficiency, Technology & Infrastructure, and Innovation & Growth, highlighting their interdependencies and strategic relevance. Read the deliverable [here](#).

SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Supporting Strategic Decision Making for Data Monetization in the Era of Digital Transformation

Abstract: this paper presents a research-based framework for data monetization strategies, developed through literature review, expert input, and ecosystem analysis.

Authors: Martin Loers, Dominik Royé and Ilyas Laihem, all from DATAMITE's partner [FIR an der RWTH Aachen](#).

Call to action

Towards a Data Monetization Maturity Model

Abstract: This paper proposes a Data Maturity Model (DMMM), the first maturity model for data monetization. It has been scientifically developed bottom up based on literature and extensive expert knowledge and its first release is extensively documented here.

Authors: Udo Bub from [1001 Lakes](#), Christos Gizelis from [OTE](#) and Rob Schneider from [FIR an der RWTH Aachen](#).

Call to action

Transforming Data Management in Telecommunications: the Case Study of OTE Group's Integration with DATAMITE project

Abstract: This paper presents an innovative framework that aims to adapt data management within the telecommunication sector in the rapidly evolving AI era.

Authors:

Achilleas Marinakis, Sotiria Petrova, Efstathia Deligeorgi, Christos Gizelis and

Michalis Kefalogiannis, all of them from [OTE](#), Vrettos Moulos from the [National Technical University of Athens](#), Vasileios Siopidis, Nikolaos Tepelidis, Konstantinos Votis and Dimitrios Tzovaras, all of them from [Center for Research & Technology Hellas](#) (CERTH).

Call to action

UPCOMING EVENTS

PARTNER PROJECT

EUROPEAN
**BIG DATA
VALUE** FORUM

datamite

DATAMITE

ORGANISED BY
BDV BIG DATA VALUE ASSOCIATION

IN COLLABORATION WITH
DTU
SDU University of Southern Denmark

ebdvf.eu
#EBDVF25

Join DATAMITE at the EBDVF 2025

The **European Big Data Value Forum (EBDVF) 2025** will take place in **Copenhagen from 12 to 14 November**. Organised by the Big Data Value Association (**BDVA**), It brings together **industry professionals, business developers, researchers and policymakers** from Europe and other regions of the world to advance policy actions and industrial and research activities in the areas of data and AI.

DATAMITE will be there for the third consecutive year, and we are very excited to be back! In addition to our Booth, **DATAMITE is organising and hosting a**

session entitled 'Data Interoperability and Monetisation: Framework, Use Cases and Market Adoption'. And as we did for the 2024 edition, we will be hosting a session with the EUDATA+ cluster, as well as sharing a 6-square-metre booth.

[Discover more](#)

Funded by
the European Union

You've received it because you've subscribed to our newsletter.

This newsletter has been prepared by the DATAMITE project, which is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them.

The DATAMITE project and its consortium partners are not liable for any consequence stemming from the reuse of this publication.

[View in browser](#) | [Unsubscribe](#)

